

April 30, 2019

Rethinking E-dating Convergence in Robert Sternberg's Triadic Paradigm and African Romance Stories: Re-Embedding the Object and Subject-Oriented Database

Author Details: Alfred Ndi

University of Bamenda-Ecole Normale Supérieure, Bambili-Bamenda-Republic of Cameroon

Email: alfredndi@yahoo.com

Abstract

This paper set out to respond to the challenge posed by scholars in postcolonial digital humanities, for peripheral sexualities to converge with archival practices of digital dating, which is a mainly objectified and technologized praxis. Drawing insights from Robert Sternberg's triadic psychological theory based on the consummation of passion, intimacy and commitment, as well as from African and oral romance stories, it came up with the conclusions that, on the one hand, Sternberg's structuralist paradigm cannot be optimized in romance narratives for reasons of the complex and changing environmental conditions. African and oral romance stories are very instructive about the deconstructive character of society when it comes to the optimalization of the consummation of these components of love. Therefore with the techno-rationalist determinism of e-dating that prioritizes efficiency over effectivity, the paper suggests that these diverging insights of African and traditional philosophy about the consummation of love can be integrated into the technological praxis in order to maximize its online educational potential, effectivity and reality. On the other hand, from these findings, the paper suggests that an archival system that converges with insights from Sternberg's triadic psychological theory and African/oral romance stories, should not prioritize only object-oriented database systems which were developed from the mid-1980s out of a need to incorporate applications beyond data processing applications served by relational database systems. Therefore, it argues for an object-oriented database that incorporates subject-oriented considerations for a greater convergence of the database management system.

Keywords

Database of e-dating, Robert Steinberg's triadic paradigm, African romance stories, object and subject-base orientations, dialectics, postcolonial digital humanities, convergence

1.0 Introduction

Postcolonial digital humanities is an interdisciplinary field of inquiry that sets itself the task of uncovering inequalities evident in digital knowledge production and remedying ideological prejudices or omissions implicated in an information-age politics of knowledge (Risam 2015, Nell 2014, Grusin 2014). [1] One of the ideological 'omissions' is the love/sexuality episteme (Koh et al. 2013, Nell 2014) [2] which is embedded in romance narratives of continental Africa. The major ideological challenge that this paper sets out to meet, and contra Hegelian exasperations with African historicism, is two-folded, at the levels of content and form. At the level of content, dating as a psychological process follows certain universally acknowledged trajectories, one of which is Sternberg's triadic love theory. But Sternberg's triadic trajectory is a structuralist and therefore *ideal* framework of romance consummation, which, together with post-structuralist insights from the oral traditions and creative writings of Africans, can open up new prospects for developing a postcolonial online dating paradigm. A re-embedding of literature's pedagogical function into Sternberg's triangle theory can expand the potentials of the postcolonial paradigm in terms of its flexibility, sensitivity to and impactability on e-dating undecidabilities. As critical scholarship upholds, philosophers (like Sternberg, oral artists and African romance writers) have described society, but the point is to *change* it. At the level of form, the digital technology can change society by re-embedding the postcolonial (Sternbergian 'consummation of love' and literary pedagogical insights) paradigm in order to potentialize its impact in the online dating universe, as prescribed by postcolonial digital humanists (Nakamura 2012a, Nakamura 2012b)? [3]

Online dating is not yet a pervasive technology that can enable all singles to meet potential partners and realize their dreams; its fringe technological determinism based on the rationalism of love is eclipsing a whole

April 30, 2019

wealth of psychological experiences that are present in the changing environment that romance literature of African artists portrays. Therefore, online dating strategies need to integrate the psychoanalytical undecidabilities (to borrow from Jacques Derrida's term) that romance characters exhibit in art. The research question for this paper is therefore as follows: how can insights from African romance stories as pedagogical works of art be inputted into Robert Sternberg's triadic consummation theory and deployed as a postcolonial archival paradigm from which to rethink the access, communication and matching services of the dating website and yield superior romantic outcomes in comparison to conventional offline dating? In order to attain this first objective, the paper deploys hypertextual analysis to first locate the current best practices in e-dating websites, and second, to interface these practices with the Sternbergian structuralist trajectories of romance consummation and the tacit insights about dating from the oral traditions and romance productions of African writers.

Several millions of people deploy e-dating services such as *eHarmony*, *Anastasiadate.com*, *Match.com*, *Chemistry.com* and the mobile dating app *Tinder*, to seek out online partners, but the majority of seekers always fail (Zytko 2014). [4] For example, in 1940, 24% of heterosexual romantic mates in the US met via family channels, 21% through school, 21% through friends, 13% through Church, 12% at a restaurant or bar, 13% through neighbours, and 10% through co-workers; but by 2009, 50% of couples met via bar, restaurant or friends, while 22% met via the digital technology, and from 2005 to 2012, more than 30% of US married couples had met online (Aziz Ansari and Eric Klinenberg 2015). [5] According to recent data, about 30% of the 7 billion people in the world now access the Internet (InternetWorldStats.com, 2011). *Match.com* scientists discovered incompatibilities between mates matched and desired; between demographic information filtered and selected dates in person (Ansari and Klinenberg, 2015). [5] E-dating algorithms facilitate people meeting and predict pretty good first dates; however, such results detail nothing about success possibilities of partners *à la longue durée*. A mathematical algorithm is unable to foretell whether two mates will make relationship material in the next ten years or so (Finkel 2012a, 2012b). [6] The digital technology *rationalizes* romance as simply an algorithmic act of swipes, 'likes', 'shares', etc, whereas love, as African oral traditions and romance stories teach us, is a complex psychological experience with ethical, social and spiritual implications determined by shifting environments of anxieties, hesitations, doubts, cues, heartbreaks, uncertainties, flaking and desires in which real people live.

While Ben Zeev (2004) [7] and Ansari and Klinenberg (2015) [5] stress intimacy as a major defining factor in e-dating, Schmitz (2016) and Zytko, et al. (2016) [8] point to frustration and exhaustion as outcomes if this factor is not considered. Rosenfeld (in Farvid 2005) [9] notes that e-dating does not follow a linear trajectory from 'loneliness' to 'happiness', and 'reciprocity' is not always the outcome because new exchange narratives intrude in the form of competition, altruism, status consistency and group gain, in the case of African American/white dating exchanges. Inter-racial couples, for example, with similar socio-economic status, educational levels, and social class level, do not necessarily attain reciprocity because of competitive discourses. Finkel et al. (2012a) [10] reports that digital daters *objectify* their online partners by educating an assessment-oriented, evaluative mindset, consequently, daters do not commit to their partners. So, objectification causes daters to make ill-advised, lazy decisions when choosing from among a large pool of prospective partners flooding their inboxes as is the practice with *AnastasiaDate Team*, *Dating.com*, etc. Finkel et al. (2012b) [11] also point out that communication periods that are too extensive, prior to a face-to-face confrontation, hurt daters' romantic prospects because daters tend to over-interpret social cues made available in communication. In the absence of a face-to-face reality check, ensuing face-to-face confrontations may engender repulsive expectation abuses. Online communication lacks the experiential wealth that one finds in an offline face-to-face meeting as evidenced in works of art marked by intuitions in love and sexual relationships. The *eHarmony* service, which is a top dating website, maintains that most dating offers to break down because of differences in personality (Zytko et al, 2016). [12] Finkel et al. (2012) [10] are also assertive that e-matching sites cannot tell what life situations the daters will face, what coping attitudes they can demonstrate and deploy in the future, and cannot foretell what interactive dynamics would eventually destabilize or even promote

April 30, 2019

romantic seduction leading to the welfare of an enduring relationship. The technology provides knowledge about age, weight, race, height, etc, but these characteristics do not necessarily constitute *attraction in themselves* without the complex attitudes and comportments that mirror real interpersonal modes of seduction. The ‘artificiality’ of photos, the classifications, etc is different from the real processes of enduring and living through interpersonal relationships with a potential mate in an environment that spawns not only chemistry but also unknowabilities, unpredictabilities and undecidabilities. As such, it is unlikely that any matching algorithm that seeks to match two people based on information available before they are aware of each other can account for more than a very small proportion of the variance in long-term romantic outcomes, such as relationship satisfaction, stability and consummation.

2.0 Review of critical literature on e-dating technology

E-dating services typically offer *access*, *communication* and *matching* services. The *praxis* in online dating sites consists of managing *access* or initial impressions through the profiles that daters post. The accumulated *profiles* of web pages give information about potential partners who can be browsed by users. Consequently, the sites expose millions of users than any partner could ever access in the offline world. In principle, web users can contact any of the new potential partners through profiling. Profiling takes the form of short paragraphs of self-description, demographic information on geographic location, age, revenue source, weight, educational level and so forth (Rosen et al. 2007, Rosen et al. 2011, Rosen n.d, Kluemper et al. 2012, Stefanone et al. 2010, Stefanone et al. 2011). [13] Based on such options for partner preferences, dating sites then offer compatibility scores. But these impressive resources of access create the illusion among daters that they can now find their soul mates online, whereas, in practice, most of the potential partners accessed by users may not reply or reply favourably. So, dating site access does not necessarily lead to access to a relationship partner; rather, it only alerts users to know that there is potential in available partners.

Compatibility scores are very prone to errors; profiles with photos are more likely to be viewed (particularly in the case of male daters seeing the pictures of female daters) than those without photos. Online management of impressions through photos alone can yield very erroneous results because a third of online photos have been judged to be ‘not accurate’ (Hancock and Toma 2009, Toma et al. 2009). [14] Photos of females have been found to be less accurate than photos of males because females use pictures of their younger years and employ professional retouching (Ibid). Self-descriptive paragraphs are also prone to the same vulnerabilities because they are a combination of descriptions of the real self and portrayals of the hoped-for self (Yurchisin, Watchravesringkan and McCabe 2005). [15] Thus, online scripted profiles are not merely written profiles but are also a way of reconstructing a dater’s identity. Particularly, during times of major social upheavals, transitions and change such as divorce re-orientation and movements from one geographical location to another, people use dating sites to re-create their identities to respond to their new situations (Yurchin et al. 2005). [16] At such a time, daters wrestle with their own consciences to determine the extent to which they have to ‘stretch the truth’ about themselves given that they aspire to meet up with their match in person eventually and at a point in time in the future when they have to construct a genuine and honest relationship (Hardey 2004a, Hardey 2004b). [17] Thus, the celebration of scientific and technological solutions to the challenge of finding a mate is now being confronted by increasing skepticism (Houran et al. 2004). [18]

Digital messages are generated by daters not only to communicate but also to create social impact. The e-mail messages daters exchange are important because they use the content of such messages to ‘screen’ up daters with potential. In the first e-mails, daters make recourse to low levels of self-disclosure, but use highly valued words that convey emotion; they describe their experience of life and interests with high emotion-laden words like ‘wonderful’ and ‘exciting’ as opposed to ‘happy’ and ‘fine’ that are less charged (Rosen 2008: 2124). [19] But the critical point here is that daters attach value to establishing *trust* by gradually getting to know their partners (Hardey 2004). [20] The *OkCupid* service cannot build *trust* only by deploying matching algorithms to enable daters to interconnect with potential partner characteristics like political affiliation, sexuality orientation, language, etc, thereby prioritizing rationalist protocols such as users’ response, a match to

April 30, 2019

yield and daters' answers, question weighting, match percentages, attraction levels, user activity and users' determination to "match" with others. In addition to dating apps like *Bumble*, *Match*, *Plenty of Fish* and *Zoosk*, *Tinder Gold* has 'add-on' premium features while *Match.com* and *Zoosk* prioritize desirable 'traits'. E-dating focuses on matchmaking in terms of clicks, profile browsing, matching algorithms and *apps* reading. The e-dating algorithm systematizes the *happenstances* of human seduction by filtering matched mates in terms of specifications on education, height, eye colour, holiday preferences, geographical location, cultural origins, ethnicity and other characteristics.

E-dating is about compatibility, prospective partners and data gathering about relationship material. Miller (2005) [21] defines e-dating as a rationalization of mate choice openness and self-closure; e-dating sites construct their mathematical algorithms on the basis of complementarity, similarity, etc, which are not valuable to the welfare of a relationship as was previously thought. The similarity is used to match demographic categories like education, religion, smoking, political ideology, preference for children, and physical traits such as race, age, eye colour, and height. *eHarmony* and *Match.com* employ photos, multiple categories, and other instruments to help daters to guess about the efficiency of their interactivity with other daters. Brown (2015) [22] notes relevantly from this light that when Christian Rudder, CEO of OkCupid and simultaneously the website's data officer, was queried, he maintained that: "We're there to get you that first date. We do use math and we do get people dates. I don't know how those dates go". OkCupid advertises that its "matching algorithm helps you find the right people." OkCupid reassures its clients that it is always A/B testing its matching methods, and tweaking for maximum outcomes and measures its success in terms of the extent to which it can stimulate conversations with responding partners: "We don't claim to evaluate you perfectly, but we do claim to find someone who claims to fulfill your claimed requirements, exactly." Nevertheless, a dating algorithm does not *pair* an individual with a partner. There is no evidence that what daters desire online can be matched to what they prefer offline. Consequently, giving daters what they desire online does not necessarily ameliorate the odds for an offline relationship. The science of randomized A/B experimentation that tests two variables means that a variable may work while another variable may not, and this is a classic flaw of science.

Tinder's service consists of offering its users photos, texting and swiping right and left, but with no guarantee that the meeting will *translate* into a genuine romantic relationship. For Tcholakian (2018), [23] this limitation signifies the specter of the lost Big Love, the 'uncanny valley' of digital mate matching. In the digital cyberspace, the dater presents themselves with curated pictures as knowledge designed to persuade. But, the dater may start to feel silly, self-representing themselves in terms of an odd smile, a measured way of talking to seduce his/her mate, and this experience can be a sickening sense of what s/he is really not. From this moment, the dating relationship may become transient and temporary as explained by Sam Lansky's essay on *Medium*, with his 'The theory of visitors,' in which tagged pictures transform into the realm of the ephemeral. Walters et al. (2011) [24] stresses on rationalization of choices with profiles of daters, data about their demographics, elevated subscription costs, etc. *Match.com* maintains that its policy is to help a dater to "put[ting] yourself out there" and "open[ing] up options". It emphasizes what it calls 'informed' choice ("Choose whom you'd like to get in touch with") and stresses on the 'efficiency' of choice rationalism ("Receive your compatible matches straight away"). Love is transformed into a rational 'product'; consequently, e-dating gives rise to a veneer of fake pictures, doubtful data and (mis)matchmaking. Gunter et al. (2017) and Gunter (2013) [25] add that rationalization of partner choice is on the basis of algorithmic calculations and this is inconsistent with interpersonalization characteristics like exploration, deviance, subtlety, etc. Questionnaires calculate compatibility (e.g. 'Are you happy with your life? Select A. Yes, B. No, C. Most of the time') and this objectifies love because e-dating is reduced to a question of personal profiles, gender markers of messaging behaviour and preference as opposed to realism and social experience. For example, the assumption is that females prefer 'revenue' and not 'physical traits' and males seek after 'physical bodies' and information strengthening 'status'. Now, this overly simplified dichotomy leaves the digital site open to 'gap filling', 'anxiety susceptibility' and 'locked in' virtual contacts with positive qualities, while anxiety rises to represent the dating self in as positive a light as possible by embellishing the desirable features of the self. Consequently, e-dating spawns fatigue,

April 30, 2019

exhilaration and fury as it compares itself to a ‘duty’ to fill the imagined gap rather than to an informally relaxed act of flirting and seeking, representing traits that are germane to seduction.

Zytko, et al. (2016) [26] conclude that daters should keep online assessment intentionally minimal in order to create in-person confrontation spaces for evaluating online seduction and personality traits. Bäck, Emma (2018) [27] provides evidence that the ‘desirability gap’ can be efficiently filled with short than with long messages. From this light, the suggestion is that, beyond the perfect profile, there is a need for *OkCupid* and the Crazy Blind Date *app* to provide just token information about mates so that in-person meetings can take place. The minimizing of profiles, chats and pictures in *e-Harmony* and *Match.com*, etc, can enable mates to rate their liking/dislike of the relational experience. Algorithms rate females according to whether they are ‘very seductive’, are ‘unlikely to appreciate males who are less handsome’ and so forth; but in an in-person Crazy Blind Date, they may possibly develop ‘chemistry’ for each other. Digital pre-selections privilege configurations, physical traits to the detriment of more personal and deeper qualities. From this light, Zajonc (in Markus 1978) [28] points out that the ‘mere exposure effect’ of repeated publicity is critical to a stimulus beyond physical appearance, preferences, confidence, and tastes. ‘First impressions’ are less powerful than gradual contact, chemistry that sparks off, an acquaintance and intimacy and other relational investments. In this light, *Tinder*, for example, simply reduces the dating experience to a simplistic evaluation of people’s pictures.

So, this right/left swipe *app* merely promotes the superficiality of faces which may lead to dating-app fatigue. *Tinder* and *Hinge* are sliding from the phase of fun toys into the phase of fatigue and frustration (Beck 2016) [29] with a foreboding of an ‘apocalypse’. *Hinge*, relaunched its dating app, in a site named as “*thedatingapocalypse.com*”. Frustration emerges from annoyance, and exhaustion arises from a lot of swiping and a sense of ‘effort’ to hook on to a partner (Ibid). By ‘bleeding users’ in this physically reductive way, there are possibilities that enthusiasm with the technology may wane because dating itself is always a disappointing and frustrating experience for most people seeking high quality relationships (Moirá Weigel 2017, *Labour of love*). [30] By way of conclusion in this section, e-dating has affordances in the digital marketing technology; however, mismatching often occurs because of the absence of face-to-face contact that can spark off passion, weak commitment, mindset shallowness, gadget fatigue, scamming, lies telling, identity theft and stalking.

3.0 Methodology

Robert Sternberg’s triadic romance theory (Sternberg 1986) [31] provides us with an ideal, universal and structural framework from which to understand the trajectory of *love* as a relationship, based on consummation of *all* of its three components, namely, *passion*, *intimacy* and *commitment*. The triangular love theory was developed by the psychologist Robert Sternberg at Yale University, who stressed upon certain structuralist functionalism of interpersonal relationships with the *consummation of all three components* being the highest, ideal and rationalist stage of romantic attainment. In his definitions, Sternberg (2007) [32] uses the term *passion* for referring to the drives that trigger physical attraction, romance, sexual gratification and related phenomena in relationships of love. The term ‘*intimacy*’ is employed to signify feelings of connectedness, likeability, closeness and bondedness in relationships of love. By *decision/commitment* is meant a variety of understandings in the short and long term; in the short-term, *decision/commitment* alludes to the decision that an individual makes to love another person, and in the long-term, it means the commitment that one makes to maintain that love through sharing of one’s life plans (Sternberg 1997, Sternberg 2004). [33] The three components of Sternberg’s theory of love are rehashed in African oral and written romance stories. However, unlike Sternberg’s structuralist and rationalist trajectory of the components, namely, the consummation of all three, the *environment* where the components evolve in the African romance stories is irrationalist, psychoanalytical, emotional and undecidable. African romance stories caution us that *sustaining* a consummate love is utopian and hardest to achieve because of the extreme difficulty of translating each of the three components of love into a single action in changing contexts and this is consistent with Sternberg’s predictions (Sternberg 1986, 1987). [34] Without a stable context of expression, even the greatest combinations of love can only but remain as an ideal. But consummating love as a complete form (i.e. *passion*, *intimacy* and

April 30, 2019

commitment) is a utopia toward which everyone strives, although the consummation of love may not be complete if only one or two of the components present in due course of time. Of the seven varieties of love combinations, consummate love is theorized to be associated with the “perfect couple.” (Sternberg 1998). [35]

The three Sternbergian components must interact optimally with each other in order to reach the consummation stage of love; but continental African stories demonstrate that the components may also interrelate with the actions they generate in order to form other types of love experiences. Non-love is an experience that refers to the absence of all three love components and this variety is masked in the vast majority of personal relationships that may simply be characterized as casual interactions (Sternberg 2004). [36] Empty love is marked by *commitment without passion* or *intimacy*. It instructs us that a stronger love may depreciate into empty love. For example, in an arranged marriage, the relationship of the spouse may start off as empty love and then develop into another form, suggesting that empty love may not be the terminal state of a long-term relationship, but the beginning (Sternberg 2004: 268). [36] Companionate love takes the form of an intimate, non-passionate love that is stronger than friendship owing to the component of long-term commitment. This love type is portrayed in a long-term marriage in which passion is no longer present (Ashford et al, 2009: 498) [37] but a deep affection and commitment have survived. This is the love between close friends who have a platonic but strong friendship.

4.0 Findings: African romance stories and postcolonializing the Sternbergian paradigm

The critical question this section sets out to answer is this: Given the structuralist ideal of Sternberg’s triadic theory of love in terms of the absolute consummation of all the components of *passion*, *intimacy* and *commitment*, what insights can African stories teach us about its attainability or deconstructibility? Clearly, the Sternbergian metanarrative fails to blossom into the full reality of love consummation when the central component is only *passion* in Joseph Ngongwikuo’s (1985) *Taboo Love*. [38] In this text, *passion* is the only component that is momentarily allowed to occasion a very rare encounter of *intimacy*. Ngongwikuo’s text portrays a context where even *intimacy* and *commitment* are completely deconstructed despite the presence of *passion*. The deconstructive environment displaces the prospects of *intimacy* and *commitment* that the indigenous lovers, Jam and Iyafi, were inventing. Although Sternberg’s paradigm of love predicts the different phases of an individual’s love for another individual, it is Ngongwikuo’s text that specifies the time or point in the love relationship when the stages evolve. Sternberg does not indicate whether the various components of love are contingent on relationship *duration* or on the particular *stage* that relationship has attained (Acker and Davis 1992). [40] Ngongwikuo’s *Taboo Love* shows that the *stage* and *interval* of the relationship are potentially significant to the love component. Jam and Iyafi instruct us that there is no accurate answer to that question, because, as a couple and, as individuals in courtship, they experience love in very complex ways and varying degrees. Jam and Iyafi fail to experience the triangle of love, as Sternberg hypothesizes, because of the taboo. Individually and collectively, they experience the components of *passion* very intensely than did Sternberg’s experimental college students. They respectively experience 'real', 'ideal' and 'perceived' passion in complex ways. The 'real' passion that Jam has for Iyafi is very profound and he expresses this only during a rare moment when he had a chance to enjoy intimacy with Iyafi. He can only meet with her at a hiding place, namely, a remote hut in the outskirts of the village, which appears to have been discovered by the *foyn*’s attendants and spies. Thus, the irregularity and inability to be *intimate* and discrete with their amorous encounters appear to have fueled their *passion* for each other evidenced when they meet in the hut during a rainy day (p. 43). Iyafi’s passion for Jam is fiery and she expresses this during her encounter with Jam; however, her intimacy suffers a setback when she is compelled to re-define *intimacy* as sharing the physical warmth of both Jam, her boyfriend and the *foyn* of Mukomangoc, whom she does not have passion for but nevertheless is forced upon her as husband. While in the short term, her *commitment* to Jam is decisive, her long term *commitment* is completely shattered to smithereens because it is subjected to taboo constraints from the palace of Mukomangoc. Jam is ritually mortified so that there is no one that Iyafi can make a long term

April 30, 2019

commitment with. In this way, love translates chiefly as passion, that is, Iyafi becomes pregnant with a child for Jam.

The 'ideal' for Jam and Iyafi shows that Jam's passion for Iyafi is a very powerful feeling of sexual attraction, but because of his adolescence and immaturity, as institutionalized by the tribe's traditions and customs, he becomes very susceptible to other feelings of hate, jealousy and anger, shown when the *foyn* decides to take his girlfriend. The ideal of passion is menaced because Jam cannot afford a discrete intimacy with Iyafi and rather depends upon the timetable of the days in the village to aspire to enjoy moments of intimacy with her. He is very conscious of the fact that he lives in a conservative society with its own deconstructive rules: he still faces many more years to qualify as an adult to eat 'bearded meat', according to the standards of Mukomangoc. It is not clear whether Jam can sustain long term commitment in the face of the paramount chief's insistence to date his girlfriend; so, this prospect of his steadfastness to commit is effaced by the death ritualized by the masquerades of the palace, and this points to their inability to consume love according to Steinberg's theoretical standards. It is not also clear whether his short term commitment is triggered by male jealousy in the face of the *foyn's* continued interest in his girlfriend or it is inborn in him or both. His ideal passion is consistent with the Sternbergian hypothesis although it is arguable whether long term effects may not have erased it. Iyafi's ideal *intimacy* with Jam is compromised by the competing intimacy of the paramount chief and the same applies to her ideal *passion* and ideal *commitment*. The 'perceived' passions for both daters are very complex in terms of how each dater is viewing the relationship. Jam thinks that he alone controls *passion* with Iyafi, but the reality is that he does not because the context of their relationship is more decisive. Iyafi thinks same with Jam but the reality is that Jam's fate is in the hands of the chief than in her hands. Jam and Iyafi feel that their *passion* is long term, but the reality is that their *passion* here is contingent on intimacy and commitment which, in turn, depends on tribal rules. Because the three separate triangles of passion, intimacy and commitment of Steinberg, do not look same as the respective triangles of Jam and Iyafi, dissatisfaction results as other scholars have predicted (Acker and Davis 1992).

Taboo Love offers a context of *testing* that complicates Sternberg's triangular paradigm of love, to a point where it is not as simple as he initially theorized it. Sternberg assessed his theory on daters who were approximately the same age (about 28 years on the average) and whose relationship duration was almost the same (that is 4 or 5 years). Jam and Iyafi are adolescents, but Ngongwikuo is in a Freudian mode of childhood sexuality and emphasizes upon the context of their dating, which is that of a conservative indigenous society in Africa at the dawn of imperial and colonial penetration, investing in its puritanistic culture while setting the stage for its own deconstruction. Steinberg's sample size is limited in terms of the diversity of characteristics. Romantic love in dating industries assumes that dating for adults is the same thing as dating for adolescents however, dating for postgraduates is not often the same thing as dating for undergraduate level couples (Acker and Davis 1992) although Ngongwikuo's narrative sample of dating is different from Sternberg's ideal triadic levels of love in terms of cultural context (Lomas 2018, Rubin 1970). [41] Ngongwikuo's text raises a major question about Steinberg's idea that sexual attraction between daters is a component of love. *Taboo Love* shows that Jam and Iyafi are sexually attracted to each other, but this may not necessarily translate into a *love* of each other because they are both aware that their dating may convert into lose of life for each of them. The sexual attraction between the daters takes place at the same time as they attempt to 'love' each other. The text shows that sexual attraction is a completely separate phenomenon from 'love' because love means the presence of life and therefore the vitalism of the physical body. In the text, bare life is threatened (that of Iyafi) and destroyed (that of Jam) and although the physical body survives (that of Jam's baby at the tale's end), the vitality of Jam's body disintegrates with his life. Sternberg's triangular theory of love has the consequence that in *Taboo Love*, it becomes a chiefly sexualized experience of physical attraction that establishes *passion* but without the *complete* trajectory of love consummation that includes intimacy and commitment. Thus, love as the consummation of intimacy and commitment is defeated in the text and only its sheer physical productivity (pregnancy) survives and partially so. More critically, Sternbergian love becomes an asexualized experience between (the dead) Jam and Iyafi at the end of the novel, as the *passion* component of the paradigm is lived

April 30, 2019

momentarily in the hiding places where both daters meet, and passion here is exclusively defined as sexual attraction. If passion means attraction in a broad sense, it is a *component* of love and not an experience that often takes place at the same time. In addition, *Taboo Love* raises a problematic when it disintegrates Sternbergian love as an integration of friendship (intimacy) and commitment. *Taboo Love* presents love as a weird experience, because, in its narrative version, love is *signified* incompletely as a passionate process that takes place without the Sternbergian commitment and intimacy; the mummified love of Jam becomes a mere spectre of Sternbergian romance. Sternberg's love paradigm undergoes an atypical refashioning in *Taboo Love* because the tendency is for a person to feel depressive or sad from a friend's absence, or to have a mutual desire to live in the same place as a friend for the rest of their lives. But love in the text appears to be celebrated as a possibility *à la* Romeo and Juliet in an *a-romantic* context where friendship (intimacy) is abstracted. *Taboo Love* reinforces the concept that sexual attraction (leading to Iyafi's pregnancy) and love are intimately disconnected and this is not consistent with the Sternbergian triangle, namely, that sexual attraction is a component of the most complete and highest kind of love. Ngongwikuo's narrative also strengthens the idea that to be friends with a dater is to be "just friends" with them, but in so doing, it devalues friendship (i.e. intimacy) as a type of meaningful relationship that a person can have as pre-condition to loving. So by trying to define love broadly, *Taboo Love* re-inscribes a context about love that deconstructs "love" as tabooed anyway.

Other African stories confirm this trajectory of tragedy in Joseph Ngongwikuo's (1985) *Taboo Love*. In George Atanga's (2015) [42] *The Last of the Virgins*, like in Talla Ngarka's (1988) [43] *The Herbalist*, the protagonists are, respectively, adolescent girls, namely, Evelyn Ndangeh from a strict Christian family who attends Our Lady of Lourdes college and Beri, living with her unmarried, conservative mother in Misaka Town, who have one thing in common with their lovers, Lesley and the transport office, namely, *passion*. Because they grew up in homes where strict religious practices and cultural customs were applied, they lose out on *intimacy* seen as sinful and on *commitment*. But they 'discover' intimacy in the township in the circumstances they were not prepared for and this jeopardizes their innocence and confuses them further about their (adolescent or adult?) identities. The outcome of the stories from the texts is their death, because *passion* fails to translate into the requisite adult states of *intimacy* and *commitment*. Sternberg says nothing in the literature about the prospect of the components destroying bare life, but literature illuminates us about this possibility. Because of *passion*, a trajectory of suicide may ensue if a relationship is determined more by the societal intrusion and if it is not properly guided in terms of intimacy and commitment. This artistic lesson is further evidenced in Nana Prah's (2015) [44] *Destiny Mine* where *passion* is de-coded into a meaningless *intimacy* without this process necessarily ending in *commitment*. The midwife, Esi Darfour, who is an experienced matchmaker, desires to get married, that is, to commit to love. But her environment gives her no luck because she is a strict conservative lady who is very selective in her love life and cannot see the type of man who is really worthy of her love. Then she meets with Dr. Adam Quarshie outside of work, but he happens to be a player like Lesley in *The Last of the Virgins* who is not willing to commit by getting married, but is only interested in intimacy, that is, to get her to bed. The relationship trajectory ends up with *intimacy* but does not proceed to a *committed* relationship as required by Sternberg's paradigm. This is where Esi's matchmaker instincts warn her to end the relationship as quickly as possible. But it is too late to end it because a continuum is already formed out intersecting *passion* and *intimacy*. Esi's and Dr. Adam Quarshie navigate in this Sternbergian continuum without optimizing it in *commitment* up to the end of the tale which is devoid of tragedy. Similarly, Edward and Gladys, who meet and are attracted to each other, indulge in empty *intimacy* but this does not translate into *commitment* in Myne Whitman's (2009) [45] *A Heart to Mend*. Societal determinism intrudes but very minimally because Gladys has difficulty in resolving her feelings to commit, as a result of her doubts over Edward's past and other social twists.

- Infatuated love results from the experiencing of *passionate* arousal but, as the story shows, there may be the absence of *intimacy* and *decision/commitment* (Sternberg 2004). Among the people of Lyela, a Gur-speaking ethnic group of a hundred and fifty thousand, living in northern Burkina Faso, tales (Dinslage 2001: 46-47) [46] are told that reflect this Sternbergian paradigm.

April 30, 2019

The story of the immured girl

A young girl is immured in a hut without door or window, so she is kept in total seclusion to prevent her from having pre-marital sexual contact with young men. Hare becomes aware of it and goes to ask his friend Squirrel to dig a tunnel for him that leads into the girl's hut. Using this tunnel, Hare succeeds in having sexual intercourse with the girl. When she finally gives birth to a baby, she is left with shame and disgrace. When the child starts to walk, all the bush animals assemble to find its father. The baby declares Hare to be its father and the latter has to obtain several rare objects that are very hard to get as bride gifts. When Hare gets hold of these bride gifts using further tricks, he is allowed to marry the baby's mother and according to this, he is accepted to act as the legitimate father of the child.

The Sternbergian motif of this tale points to anxieties among the Lyela to repress intimacy with girls as a way of protecting their girl children from passionate encounters that may lead to pre-marital (committed) sexual relationships. The tale is implicated in the 'repression' of intimacy, that is, in the importance that is given to the virginity of women and to the management of marriageable girls in Lyela society. Lyela girls are like Evelyn and Beri in *The Last of the Virgins* and *The Herbalist*; they are cautioned to desist from pre-marital sex and are warned about the possible disaster that can be triggered from such an involvement. But more critically, the Sternbergian motif points to the advent of primitive capitalism in this society with references to forms of materialism and capitalism such as 'rare objects' alluded to in the tale as a pre-condition to sexual access and marital status. This is consistent with Michel Foucault's (1979, 1980, 1992, 1990) [47] theory of the sexual episteme in which he explains that 'repressive sexuality' came about recently in human history with the advent of capitalism. The tale aims to generate feelings of shame, fear and avoidance in girls who contemplate to indulge themselves in intimacy with men and pre-marital sexuality. The romantic relationship in the text starts out as infatuated love and becomes romantic love as intimacy develops over time. The story teaches us that, in indigenous African societies, the belief is that, without developing intimacy and eventually commitment, infatuated love may disappear suddenly. But the story also tells us that this Sternbergian motif is deconstructible even through the employment of deceptive techniques. Sternbergian love can be consummated in traditional African societies.

Continental African stories portray other varieties of uncompleted love, which fall short of consummate love, as theorized in the 'perfect couple' discourse of Sternberg. The narratives re-place the theory within the context of what has been called "a broader interest in taxonomising that has now become a major feature of the field" of personal relationships (Goodwin 2013:12). [48] *Intimacy* is one of the Sternbergian components that emerge in many African stories in a nontrivial sense, when a set of feelings are experienced in a relationship characterized as friendship. Friendship generates closeness, bondedness and warmth toward the other partner, but it may also generate sparks of fury clothed by feelings of intense passion, as in Amara's (2014) [49] *Black Sparkle Romance*, without a commitment that is long-term (Sternberg 2004: 266). Ola Awonubi's (2016) [50] *Love's Persuasion* starts off with life in the city of Lagos and the fate of a company named as the Lagos firm City Finance. But the focus of the author is on Ada Okafor, a beautiful accountant, who engages with a British-trained assistant managing director, Tony Okoli, in a Sternbergian trajectory of *intimacy*. Ada Okafor and Tony Okoli shares one thing in common which brings them together, namely, their enjoyment of book reading. Books draw them closer into *intimacy* and they soon fall passionately in love. But their love of books which facilitates *intimacy* and leads to *passion* does not end up in *commitment*, which is the absolute Sternbergian pre-condition for a complete love consummation. The text shows that commitment is deconstructible by societal narratives such as jealous colleagues, Tony's disapproving family members, social status and so on which test their passion for each other. Despite these environmental factors, their passion for each survives but without triggering the necessary *commitment*. The text ends with the lesson that passion can trump environmental challenges but also points to the power of society to deconstruct love. When in Amina Thula's (2015), [51] *Elevator Kiss: A Tale of Love*, Sindi meets with Edward in a Cape Town building, the elevator becomes the first site of *intimacy* where *passion* is ignited. Her office and the important projects they try to realize become the second site of *intimacy* that eventually tilts the balance from *intimacy* and *passion* to

April 30, 2019

the prospect of *commitment* despite the disappointments in Sindi's previous amorous relationships. The text ends without any commitment stated by any of the daters, but the anticipation created is very high. It suggests that environmental factors like disappointments in previous relations must be challenged in order to attain the Sternbergian level of consummate love.

Some activities of *intimacy* may not end up at all in *passion*, and, speak less of, in *commitment*. The creative and photographic activities of Mira and Dominic in the Black Sparkle magazine create fury rather than romance in Amara Nicole Okolo's *Black Sparkle Romance*. When Christy Inemi-Spiff realizes that Joshua does not reciprocate her feelings of *passion* in Kiru Taye's *Bound To Passion*, she decides to uncommit to the relationship. However, Joshua wants to strengthen commitment by reinforcing intimacy. His idea of intimacy is spending a quiet Christmas on a remote African Island in order to salvage their relationship during a period of two weeks. But the doubt that Inemi-Spiff cultivates compromises the prospect of a durable commitment and of a consumable love. These examples may be referred to as cases of abortive *intimacy*. When Emem Akpan, heartbroken, ends her relationship with her fiancé for his unfaithfulness in Amaka Azie's (2019) [52] *Love At First Sound*, the Sternbergian paradigms of *passion*, *intimacy* and *commitment* are compromised. But when Yomi, a younger man, meets her and ignites flames of passion in her Lagos apartment, this represents the moment when intimacy is given a chance to consolidate *passion* and *commitment*. Now, intimacy fails because, at this critical moment, he learns about a troubling secret of betrayal concerning her, which compromises commitment to the relationship.

The stories show that romantic love may start from a combination of the *passionate* and *intimate* components of love. In other words, romantic lovers are not only attracted physically to each other but may also be bonded emotionally (Sternberg 2004: 268); they may be bonded both intimately and passionately, but without sustaining commitment.

- *Commitment* itself may not trigger *intimacy* nor *passion* in any order or in combination. Tishe and Adnan cannot share love in Affinnih's (2015) [53] *A Tailor-made Romance*, although Adnan is committed to the relationship. Adnan is dedicated to the relationship with Tishe, because he introduces Tishe to his family and plans romantic getaways. In spite of this dedication, and the rare moment of sharing a goodnight kiss, commitment leads to an abortive outcome in the relation for reason of social class differentiation. Tishe is horrified when she discovers that Adnan is what she considers as a mere tailor. She vows that no second date will ever take place after this revelation. Social class becomes a critical point that deconstructs the igniting of desire in Tishe for Adnan. Elsewhere, love cuts across social class, but in the text, Tishe's relationship with Adnan is intransitive. Although Beba rescues Kambi from an attack whose outcomes could have been fatalistic in Chioma Iwunze-Ibiam's (2016) [54] *Finding Love Again*, they only come close to having a relationship but nothing more as Kambi pushes him away. Beba becomes a 'fake fiancé' to Kambi who has to begin seeking love all over again.
- Cultural factors have a great impact on the way people feel about love and select dates for marriage, that is, for commitment. In western societies, love comes before marriage; but in non-western societies, such as Pakistan, India and Africa, marriage comes not necessary with love, but because the person has other qualities like being a paramount chief (Ngongwikuo's *Taboo Love*) and other qualities (Levine et al. 1995), [55] shared interests, loneliness and unplanned pregnancy (Baron and Byrne 1994). [56] Consequently, this increases social anxiety which is tied to interpersonal relations because a dater who anticipates negative outcomes with a person, for these cultural reasons, may tend to avoid that person. Anxiety may also be caused by real events like sexual infidelity, teasing and unreturned phone calls. Consequently, cultural values and social anxiety may impact negatively on intimacy and commitment and consummate love may not be actualized if these are absent. In this context, love may get lost over time and may not translate into marriage, for example. In Sifa Asani Gowon's (2016) [57] *A Taste of Love*, the components of *intimacy* and *passion* are the only factors present. They take multiple forms in the text. Toby, the manager of the lounge named as the Bar-rage, attracts the single mother and cake baker Adoo Ibi thanks to his tasty pizza, as well as his good looks and calm, confident temperament. Adoo is excited because Toby accepts to house both her

April 30, 2019

and her son, and Toby is seduced to Adoo because of her simple manners and sense of autonomy. These activities of *intimacy* give both daters the impression that they had known each other for a long time. This translates into *passionate* encounters and confirms the dictum that: the way to a (wo)man’s heart is through his (her) stomach. But *intimacy* and *passion* without *commitment* cannot engender love. Gowon’s *A Taste of Love* portrays the context of previous love experiences in which they were hurt and shows how they cause both daters to hesitate to commit. The pasts of Toby and Adoo become the determining factors over the present question of *commitment*. *A Taste of Love* therefore depicts relational devaluation as an outcome from such encounters, that is, from the perception that the other person may not value the relation as much as one does (Baumeister and Tice 1990). [59] From feeling anxious, people tend to develop more feelings than anxiety such as anger, guilt, and distress that may compromise prospects of realizing the three Sternbergian components of love. Similarly, Adaora’s teenage romance with the music star, Aristar in Amaka Azie’s (2016) [60] *Melodies of Love*, fails to materialize into a commitment because of a disastrous heartbreak that took place twelve years ago and this shattered her trust in men. Consequently, she builds a ‘fortress’ around her heart and finds it difficult to trust Aristar anymore because of the bitter past she had experienced in love. Consequently, she is not comfortable with prospective cases like Ikenna, a highly paid musician, who is famous, rich and committed.

In light of these findings, the following survey result summarizes the postcolonial paradigmatic guide for an integrated digital dating archival system.

	Title of text	Sternberg’s triadic component present	Outcomes of a love relationship	Social/critical factors responsible	Approximative level of consummation achieved out of the ideal level of 100%
1	Joseph Ngongwikuo (1985) <i>Taboo Love</i>	Passion	Deconstruction of intimacy and commitment	Conservative tradition, material historicism	30%
2	George Atanga (2015) <i>The Last of the Virgins</i>	Passion	Deconstruction of intimacy and commitment	Social change from traditional to modern society	30%
3	Talla Ngarka (1988) <i>The Herbalist</i>	Passion	Deconstruction of intimacy and commitment	Social change from traditional to modern society	30%
4	Nana Prah (2015) <i>Destiny Mine</i>	Passion, and limited Intimacy	Absence of commitment	Very high standards of selecting partner, liberal characters who are sexual players	50%
5	Myne Whitman (2009) <i>A Heart to Mend</i>	Passion, and Intimacy	No commitment	Doubts over partner’s past life and other social twists.	60%
6	The people of Lyela in northern Burkina Faso ‘The story of the immured girl’	Passion, intimacy and commitment	Attempts to deconstruct passion, intimacy and commitment	Materialism and capitalism in traditional societies	80%
7	Amara (2014) <i>Black Sparkle Romance</i>	Passion and intimacy (friendship)	No long term commitment	Intense fury	60%
8	Ola Awonubi (2016) <i>Love’s Persuasion</i>	Passion and intimacy	No commitment	Jealous colleagues, disapproving family members, social status	50%
9	Amina Thula (2015), <i>Elevator Kiss: A Tale of Love</i>	Passion and intimacy	No commitment	disappointments in previous relations	60%
10	Kiru Taye, <i>Bound To Passion</i>	Passion (unreciprocated)	Abortive intimacy No commitment	Doubts, lack of understanding	40%
11	Amaka Azie (2019) <i>Love At First Sound</i>	Passion	No intimacy	Unfaithfulness, betrayal	30%
12	Affinnih (2015) <i>A Tailor-</i>	Occasional	No passion	social class	60%

April 30, 2019

	<i>made Romance</i>	intimacy, commitment		differentiation	
13	Chioma Iwunze-Ibiam (2016) <i>Finding Love Again</i>	None	No passion, no intimacy, no commitment	Deception	10%
14	Asani Gowon (2016) <i>A Taste of Love</i>	Passion and intimacy	No commitment	Past love life that still hurts, the other partner does not value the relationship as much as one does and desires	50%
15	Amaka Azie (2016) <i>Melodies of Love</i>	Unreciprocated commitment	No intimacy, no passion	Bitter past love life shatters trust in men, the influence of social circles	30%

African romance stories do not only function to entertain, but they also function to teach. From this survey results, we learn from the romance stories that Sternberg’s triadic theory of love is structurally utopic because certain critical and social factors deconstruct its attainability by undercutting the dialectical relationship between passion, intimacy and commitment. These factors as elucidated by the oral tradition of literature and works of art are: Conservative tradition, material historicism, social change from traditional to modern society, elevated standards of selecting partner, the ambiguous role of sexual players, doubts over partner’s past life and other social twists, doubts over other issues, lack of understanding, disappointments in previous relations, materialism and capitalism in traditional societies, intense fury, jealous colleagues, disapproving family members, differences in social status, unfaithfulness, betrayal, partners who do not value a relationship as desired and bitter past love life that shatters trust.

This postcolonial paradigm which is both structuralist and post-structuralist is what has been termed as “compulsive thinking, [or] *abstract* thinking... directed towards systematization and categorization; it is theoretical instead of real” (Fenichel 1963). [60] Consequently, in order to make it real, the next section of the paper will propose a postcolonial digital marketing strategy of e-dating that can be immediately applicable in order to re-construct its critical landscape in terms of romantic access, communication and matching (Skyner and Cleese, 1994: 364). [61] Love is actually one of those life areas where 'success' is contingent on the deployment of both ‘explicit’ and ‘tacit’ knowledge acquired through theory and practice (Kuhn 1970: 44). [62]

5.0 Discussions

The findings in the above section suggest that, in addition to the *praxis* of e-dating based on scientific and rationalistic determinism, the technological *code* should be reinforced with a new ethos of online communication management that incorporates literary insights. Human beings have evolved in the Darwinian sense and are hard wired with strong Freudian urges to form the optimal ideal state of Sternbergian romantic relationships. But African stories show that finding an *appropriate* partner is very challenging. The oral text, in particular, from Burkina Faso shows that it is helpful to get occasional assistance, just as *Hare becomes aware ...and goes to ask his friend Squirrel to dig a tunnel for him that leads into the girl’s hut*. In other oral traditions (such as the *khastegari* customs of Iran, the arranged marriages in Southeast Asia and the Jewish *shadchan* glorified in the musical *Fiddler on the Roof*), old millennial traditions of romantic relationships from deliberate third party interventions to chance encounters are deployed (Coontz 2005). The resources utilized included social networks, willingness to enforce judgments about the actualization of couples and strong opinions about people (Ahuvia & Adelman, 1992). [63] The desire to find a romantic partner has endured into the present day, but the challenges have increased as the stories testify. All the resources available for addressing these challenges today cannot be found in the ubiquity of the Internet. The internet provides the basic infrastructure for that purpose, but it needs support from offline technological inputs. Therefore, the critical question this section sets out to answer is as follows: Given the idealism of the e-dating technology based on scientific and rationalistic determinism, and in the light of the insights that African stories have illuminated about the *unattainability* of Sternbergian triadic love in the sections above, what additional technologies can be integrated and deployed in e-dating in order to optimize its archival efficiency and effectivity?

April 30, 2019

On this very critical question of trust, which African stories raise as a factor that impedes commitment to love, exclusively online relationships are different from exclusively offline relations in the sense that online daters have the absolute option to break a relationship by not responding to any emails or by blocking further ones from coming to their inboxes. They may also move to other anonymous emails that they have secured. Now the critical factor of *trust* can only be constructed from the Sternbergian components of *intimacy* and *passion*. The digital technology does not provide such an affordance of *intimacy* and *passion* in real terms. So, one of the greatest challenges for e-daters is how to deal with the feeling of awkwardness that is inevitable prior to meeting for the first time with someone that one has so little knowledge and *trust* about. And yet, they must live with the awkwardness because they long to have an intimacy and hopefully a passionate relationship with their partners, which only a face to face encounter can afford. Consequently, it is clear that daters who use only the online medium achieve lesser intimacy and passion in comparison with offline daters in face to face relationships (Scot, Mottarella and Lavooy 2006). [64] It is also clear that the Sternbergian component of commitment is the best predictor of the relationship maintenance behaviours that can be employed to sustain dating relationships. Among these relationship behaviours there is openness, confidence, assurance and positiveness. Therefore, we can predict that ‘virtuals’ or daters who first met online and are still meeting online will have a very low level of propensity to trust and commitment. ‘Pinochios’ or daters, who first met online and are now meeting offline will have a low level of propensity to trust and commitment. ‘Real worlders’ or daters who met offline and are now meeting offline will have a comparatively higher level of propensity to trust and commitment. And ‘cyber emigrants’ who first met offline and are now meeting online will have a relatively high level of propensity to trust, commitment and relationship maintenance. These modes must incorporate communication of identities and impressions that is sensitive to specific digital behaviours (emotionality, self-disclosure, relationship maintenance), together with the communication of their effects. The modes must articulate *variance* and not only *uniformity* in the sensitivities of daters, can be communicated. Beyond access, communication and matching, it is critical for websites to offer dating advice, scientific studies of romantic relationships and personality evaluations, because these features can have important benefits, and they can impact on individual daters.

This paper suggests that a website that aims to address the triadic consummation paradigm of Sternberg should be critical in its multi-functionality and flexibility. It should enable users to meet potential romantic partners by introducing singles to persons wishing to form not only dating but also marital relationships. It should facilitate self-selection services for browsing profiles of prospective partners with a focus not only on the general population of online daters but also from a specific subpopulation (PlentyOfFish, Match, OkCupid) or niche self-selection from a specific population (SugarDaddie, JDate). It may enable not only users’ friends but also family members to play the role of matchmaker for them (HeartBroker, Kizmeet). It may also facilitate live interaction between users thanks not only to avatar-based virtual functioning (OmniDate, VirtualDateSpace, Weopia) but also webcam-based video dating (Video dating, WooMe, SpeedDate,). Matching may be founded on users’ self-report data (Chemistry, eHarmony, PerfectMatc) as well as non-self-report data, like genetic data (ScientificMatch, GenePartner, FindYourFaceMat) with the use of GPS (global-positioning-system)-based smartphone apps to inform users about potential partners in their vicinity (Badoo, Zoosk, Grindr).

In addition to these classical functions, a postcolonial dating website will dialectize its hypertexts with offline personal advertising of romantic relationships as in newspaper sites and Craigslist, casual encounters for hookups (AdultFriendFinder, OnlineBootyCall, GetItOn), group dating with strangers (Meetcha, Ignighter, GrubWithU), social networking to meet friends of friends (MySpace, Facebook, Friendster) and multi-player online games to enable users meet partners by employing avatars in the online environment (TheSims, SecondLife, WorldOfWarcraft). Matrimonial sites as in Indian websites and speed-dating, a dating method created in the 1990s where users attend a special occasion online in order to engage in a number of brief face-to-face exchanges with potential romantic partners and then decide. Although it may sound old-fashioned, personal advertisements for matrimonial dating that had existed in history and was strengthened by the newspaper and magazine, can be integrated in the digital technology to publicize partners. This can take the

April 30, 2019

form of printed personal advertisements and pen pals particularly in unusual contexts, such as war and environments of highly asymmetric sex ratios, where groups of individuals are isolated from potential partners. In this forum, the advertiser provided a portrait of their qualities and desired qualities of their ideal partner, the type of relationship sought, followed by responses. Now, the qualities and responses may need to be analyzed by being subjected to survey results (Simenauer & Carroll 1982, Laumann, Gagnon, Michael, & Michaels, 1994) [65] as illustrated in the findings section above.

A pervasive e-dating system that integrates literary pedagogy must consider adopting human matchmaking, which was used in history and its practice is described in Jewish, Biblical, Islamic, African and other religious discourses. Indigenous matchmaking is a role that was often played by *rabbis*, the clergy, priests, and elderly, respected personalities in traditional communities, and this service was actively sought after by parents searching for partners for their matured children and by single adults dissatisfied with outcomes from other options for seeking a partner. Today's pervasive digital matchmaking may therefore have to expand its horizon from mathematical algorithms to incorporate users of the service that the manager of the system has got to know privately. In this case, human matching decisions would have to typically assimilate the rich experiences and intuitions that are portrayed in African stories, and which also exist in western and other non-western societies (Adelman & Ahuvia, 1991, Woll & Cozby 1987). [66]

The e-dating system may integrate video-dating, as a platform for mate seeking that involves members providing descriptions of their profile *together* with photographs, followed by participations in videotaped interviews (Woll & Cozby 1987, Ahuvia & Adelman 1992). [67] In order to select dating prospects, an initial screening can be done based on the photos and information profiles and then a viewing of the videotapes can follow. As we have seen from the African stories, there are social cues that users may need to capture meaning from and which are capable of triggering interest. Users can then express interest in meeting with specific persons, and, if the interest becomes mutually *passionate*, contact information can be exchanged and the respective pairs can then have a face-to-face meeting in view of facilitating *intimacy*. Although personal advertisements and video-dating are fringes rather than mainstream methods to meeting prospective partners, they can still address the problems of a percentage of users that mainstream digital methods may not.

In the same way as we were able to 'listen' to protagonists tell their tales in African romance stories, so too the enhanced e-dating website should enable millions of subscribers to do the same online so that the manager can get familiar with his users by analyzing the massive heaps of data. From the stories told, the personal information, messaging, app use, etc, the manager can develop patterns that can determine *content* for users. This is similar to OKCupid's analysis of user information to create *OKTrends*, a blog that publishes content relevant to dating and popular culture. In this forum, the stories of couples (as told in the African romance tales) can be highlighted as specific themes. In Match.com, the stories are thematized under 'love at first sight', 'happy nuptials', 'baby births', and so forth. Their appeal to users is that they entertain irrespective of whether they are a nice story with a romantic or a tragic ending. Other platforms of digital marketing may also be used to portray the insights that African romance literature portrays in its structuralist (scripted) or post-structuralist (societal) forms. In this light, the *PlentyofFish* site analyzes user profiles, but also releases *YouTube* content and blogposts. The *YouTube* content can then be deployed to cater to a user audience that is located beyond the mainstream user group, explaining the relationship challenges and giving dating advice.

6.0 Conclusion

By way of a conclusion, this paper has gestured to the post-structuralist maxim that: 'philosophers have hitherto only interpreted the world in various ways; the point is to change it' (Tassie 2010: 86). [68] The concept of love as sexuality, intimacy and engagement, has been described by philosophers in African oral traditions and romance stories as an 'essence-free' feeling (to borrow the term from the philosopher Slavoj Zizek), a sphere of the Freudian 'irrational' with its own spontaneity, emotional unpredictability, impulsivity and erraticism. This is consistent with the ethos of 'breaking' in the field of postcolonial digital humanities. However, the real challenge is the ethos of 'building' and 'sharing', that is, the deployment of digital

April 30, 2019

technology to transform that world into a better society for humans to live in. The current attempt to ‘change it’ consists in deploying the technology to turn love into an objectified ‘product’ of rational choice-making, which is regulated by capital through digital systems of data collection, and fuelled by consumerism, utilitarianism, expediency, etc. For example, Facebook promotes what is referred to as ‘contact-less friendships’ by minimizing the complexity of love to LOLs, inane innuendos and pokes. Current online dating is appropriating love in terms of qualities of objectification and positivism in ways which are disembedded from its qualities of spirituality.

This paper argues that in its historical evolution, the e-dating site should incarnate the ‘spiritual’ dimensions that the philosopher artists and writers of Africa have described. The French essayist François de la Rochefoucauld once declared that genuine love is like a ghost: people *speak* about it, but very few have really *seen* it for sure. Taking on from that stream of perception, Alain Badiou (2009) [69] reinforced this point in a book *Éloge de l'amour*, namely, that it is possible to have love rationally (‘Ayez l'amour sans le hasard!’) and to be in love without falling in love (‘On peut être amoureux sans tomber amoureux!’). But this is the online version of dating that prioritizes rationalism. In this way, it can be said that e-dating is challenged by an ‘ambiguous status’ of love as a divided idiom in the Bakhtinian sense of the term (Bakhtin 1982, 1984, 1986), [70] with its language of the rational’ and its language of the ‘irrational’. The ‘rational’ language of love is being fuelled by e-dating through economic factors and material conditions like digital technologies. But it is the ‘irrational’ idiom of love narrated by African philosophers that constructs the ‘rational’ part. In Karl Marx’s ‘Unpublished manuscripts’, our attention is drawn to the fact that justice in the economic and material relationships of a given society can be gleaned from the type of relationships that women and men uphold in such a society. Marx equates such an affective relationship with an evident fact, namely, the degree to which nature for human kind is reducible to human essence or human nature has transformed into human essence according to human beings. So, such a relationship can tell us the degree of attainment of mankind’s level of development (Levine 1976). [71] When post-Marxist scholar Alain Badiou published his *In Praise of Love* (following a film produced by Godard with that title), he drew inspiration from this Marxist philosophy to highlight a chief preoccupation with online dating, namely, that online dating systematically avoids the ‘event of love’ as a necessarily *chance-encounter*. This essential sanctity of love as ‘an event’ is an idea that online dating needs to retrieve from philosophy. In the context of online dating, Badiou’s logic draws from the utopic, truth-procedure concept, which attaches greater value to chance-encounter as opposed to an online encounter. From this light, online dating is about material alienation in the abstract sense and so the prospect of imagining that some events may take place to overcome challenges associated with chance-encounter are very minimal in the online version.

This paper has demonstrated that although e-dating epitomizes technological alienation, which is a major problematic decried by postcolonial digital humanities scholars, this does not, however mean that online dating is absolutely alienating in and for itself. As a metanarrative, online dating has always been in flux; it is a process of self-presentation and matching that revolves around selection rather than around offline *interactivity*. In app swiping, people concentrate on the quantification of potential mates seen (profiles, demographics, etc) rather than on quality as emphasized by African traditional and modernist philosophers. So, e-dating suffers from the question of the paradox of choice, namely, the idea that having multiple choices may seem good, but it is actually a bad one. E-dating ‘freezes up’ in the face of multiple options because users cannot effectively decide who to date seriously, for example, on *Tinder*. Even when they make the decision, there is the tendency to be unsatisfied with their choices, because they start to think about all the other girlfriends or boyfriends they could have dated instead. This creates paralysis in dating as a result of the illusion of plentifulness, of an ocean of easily-accessible singles. In the end, the feeling is that the dating app delivers something else other than a mate relationship; it conveys a certain sensation of possibility, of a chance that they *could* but never succeeded. The dating app functions as a *totem* that is carried around to deflect the despair of singleness. The sense of infinite online possibility impacts negatively in the real-world context of the social. For example, the old circles of bars are no longer frequented as before: the apps disincentivize daters from attempting offline romantic opportunities

April 30, 2019

because apps just feel easier and they are low-stake. In the event where things do not work out, the dater would feel that s/he was only a stranger and one did not embarrass oneself in an awkward relationship of requesting an outing in person that did not work.

As a means of communication, online dating sites and apps do not instruct daters on *how* to date; they do not offer *clear norms, or knowledge of exactly what one is searching for* and sometimes give inaccurate impressions (e.g. women: long-term relationship, men: casual sex, friendship, cooperation, etc). This causes daters not to be authentic with their profiles. They ‘chill’ out preferring to see how things turn out first without really *desiring* a particular direction for things to go. Daters ‘chicken’ out without a ‘dating language’ nor a desire to ‘confess’ their deeper wishes, confusion or frustration (to borrow the term from Michel Foucault). Thus, instead of staying in the metanarrative paradigm of mate-choice, daters have the propensity to ‘freeze’ by internalizing embarrassment and residual shame about, for example, stereotypes from racial, ethnic, class, disability, generational considerations. This then leads to exhaustion and even harassment. The reason for this post-moderning effect is that the metanarrative environment of mate-choice is not enriched with ‘grammatical’ rules of dating that African oral traditions and written stories provide in their subtle scripts of courtship itineraries embedding a certain power and knowledge dynamics, following Michel Foucault’s dialectics (1979, 1980, 1990, 1992). [72] The e-dating apps only stress the technology of options, connections and inter-connections; the rest is the postmodern realm of the *unknowable*, the *unpredictable* and the *undecidable* that African oral traditions and written stories portray so well. In the sense of *praxis*, which postcolonial digital humanists have the propensity to invoke, it is not the fault of the digital technology itself to rationalize its treatment of love; it is the fault of the absence of postmodern facilitation of the dating websites, apps and applications, perhaps because we live in an epoch of scarcity of time when people are afraid of wasting time with the literary or imaginative elements of love. From this Foucauldian light, digital technology offers the efficiency of method (*power*), but not effectivity of content (*knowledge*).

E-dating has been referred to as an apocalypse waiting to happen (Gray 2016); [73] that is, as another manner in which modernization of life overworks how people get into feeling a sense of awkwardness. African romance writings teach us that even though an e-dater may not be attracted to a mate at first sight, they may be seduced to them over time, as s/he gets to understand them better. Consequently, assessing a mate’s suitability in the span of one digital date or a single swipe, definitely eliminates this possibility of knowledge. Even with an initial seduction, time is necessary to construct intimacy and commitment. From this perspective, there is a conflict between the *efficiency* and *effectivity* of dating. The digital language of efficiency sounds good; however, the critical question is this: efficiency for *what purpose?* Digital apps are an efficient technology that enables a dater to move through their options. But the more a resource is deployed efficiently, the more it runs the risk of being used up if its purpose is not circumscribed. The idea of exposing oneself digitally multiple times can be exhausting because the desire for efficiency also plays out in the offline context of the apps where the e-dater ends up expending minimal effort on a huge number of dates and believes this is the location of the culture of his burnout (Beck 2016, Bethuel 2018). [74] So, the multiples of e-dates attended to artificially may add up to a general feeling that the dater has done pretty much a labouring work, whereas she is still left out with virtually nothing.

This paper has addressed itself to this stone-walling form of love encounter where the screen separates both potential partners, and defers the humanism of face-to-face interaction. It has argued that the e-technology may exacerbate the affective pains of daters who are extricated from the interaction-based process of the love generation. In online processing of love, daters deploy *concepts* in their mindsets to guess acceptance and rejection possibilities by other daters. Online love processing is thus artificial because acceptance or rejection of love by daters is about acceptance or rejection of the *perceived* or *imagined* traits of daters’ categories rather than about acceptance or rejection of *real* dating, physical persons. E-dating profiles reduce three-dimensional individuals to two-dimensional ones and this kind of display of information fails to capture important experiential values from social interaction which are necessary to assess compatibility with prospective daters. Works of literature and discourse can *signify* a genuine diversity of human experiences and characteristics, the

April 30, 2019

real interpersonal processes that create the feeling of love. Love is constructed through the signification of communication in which perceptions are certified and invalidating evaluations of inaccurate interpersonal experience are disconfirmed. Online dating does not offer the dater the opportunity to make such checks and balances. The algorithmic science retrieves information from two individuals who are absolutely unaware of the existence of each other and cannot determine whether they are emotionally, physically, socially culturally and spiritually compatible. The paper has shown through African romance writings that compatibility cannot be 'measured', interest in particular partners does not automatically signify that they constitute their ideal or perfect algorithmic match and compatibility cannot be established from a data of traits about an individual through the algorithm of a matchmaker or profiling because complementarity and similarity have little to do with the *quality* of emotions found in love relationships.

In place of the current practice, the paper proposes an e-dating pedagogy of the Eros with insights drawn from African (as well as other e.g. Austen 1993) [75] creative philosophies of love where *Eros* takes the turn to regenerate the desire to converse. Online participation should be informed by the *Eros* myth (Hakim 2010) [76] which has potentials for expansive reproduction and maintenance of the digital system. The African perspective to love articulates a social construction from historical, economic, cultural, religious and 'traditionalist' factors. It is sensitive to traditionalist factors like stigmatization of love, especially for teenage girls in Africa and elsewhere, dominant sexual ideologies on 'good behaviour' focused on the idea that 'sex is wrong' and girls who have experienced it have been 'spoilt', as well as the frustrations of the young male dater whose relationship with his environment is thoroughly ambiguous (e.g. Atanga 1985, Ngarka 1988, Ambanasom 2010). [77] It raises hypertextual issues with the question of love as concealment, secrecy and stigma and as rationalist technological framing. Online dating should therefore prioritize not only rationalism but also *eroticism* in the communication context of *autopoiesis* marked by algorithms, code, medium, but also by irony, playfulness, double entendres, feeling, lines, humour, compliments discussions, glances, flirting, interaction, attitudes, symbol, drives, nonsense talk, cuddling, nicknames and so forth (Luhmann 2000, 1995, 1999). [78] The African romance philosophers have instructed us that, beyond smilies, emoticons on MSN, such as winking, role-plays, etc, there is mystery, ambivalence, face-to-face encounter, the seduction process of humour, self-disclosure, confession, impulse and the maturing of thought (Ricoeur 1991), [79] the evaluation of love in terms of trust, trust-creating, confidence, risk. Beyond the deployment of a webcam, there is a contrast between texting and intention (Bjerrum 1995). [80] Given the meteoric rise of the digital technology in this age and time, its ubiquity and power (Castells 2011), [81] the new e-dating website should become a dialectical 'teacher' of love as cultural reproduction (Garrison 1997, Gadamer 1983), [82] as a dialogical strategy of rhetorics that approximates the Athenian Golden Age myth of learning as a cultural act handed down from teacher to pupil in Spartan warrior society. From the suggestions of African philosophers of love in their artistic productions, especially at the level of commitment, love should be inscribed in the digital technology as *fusion*, as an encounter not only of two *persons*, but also a meeting of two families. The digital teacher should identify love beyond knowledge by integrating experience, it should combine principles and practice, reflexivity and values, online and offline media, the writing technology and the oral peripheralities, the verbality of desire and the kinesic gestures, paralinguistic tonalities and intonations that (dis)confirm it, the cognition of emotion and its skills and the body of love and its mind (Hooks 1994: 199). [83]

-There are no conflicts of interest in this work

-This work is self-produced without any funding by any organization

Works Cited

- i. Risam, Roopika. "Beyond the margins: Intersectionality and the digital humanities." *DHQ: Digital Humanities Quarterly*, Volume 9, Number 2 (2015). Nell Smith, M., 2014. "Frozen Social Relations and Time for a Thaw: Visibility, Exclusions, and Considerations for Postcolonial Digital Archives." *Journal of Victorian*

April 30, 2019

- Culture*, 19(3), pp.403-410, Grusin, Richard. "The dark side of digital humanities: Dispatches from two recent MLA conventions." *Differences* 25.1 (2014): 79-92.
- ii. Nell Smith, M., 2014. "Frozen Social Relations and Time for a Thaw: Visibility, Exclusions, and Considerations for Postcolonial Digital Archives." *Journal of Victorian Culture*, 19(3), pp.403-410, Koh, Adeline, and Roopika Risam. "Open Thread: The Digital Humanities as a Historical 'Refuge' from Race/Class/Gender/Sexuality/Disability?." *Postcolonial digital humanities* (2013)
- iii. Nakamura, Lisa. "Queer female of color: The highest difficulty setting there is? Gaming rhetoric as gender capital." *Ada: A Journal of Gender, New Media, and Technology* 1.1 (2012a). Nakamura, Lisa. "'It's a Nigger in Here! Kill the Nigger!'" *User-Generated Media Campaigns Against Racism, Sexism, and Homophobia in Digital Games*. "The international encyclopedia of media studies (2012b)
- iv. Zytko, Douglas, Sukeshini A. Grandhi, and Quentin Jones. "Impression management struggles in online dating." *Proceedings of the 18th international conference on supporting group work*. ACM, 2014.
- v. Ansari, Aziz, and Eric Klinenberg. "How to make online dating work." *The New York Times* (2015): 6.
- vi. Finkel, E, Eastwick, P, Benjamin, R and Reis K, 2012a, 'Online dating: a critical analysis from the perspective of psychological science', *Psychological Science in the Public Interest* 13(1):3-66 DOI: 10.1177/1529100612436522 Finkel, Eli J., et al. "Dating in a digital world." *Scientific American Mind* 23.4 (2012b): 26-33.
- vii. Ben Zeev, A., 2004, *Love Online: Emotions in the Internet*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- viii. Schmitz, Andreas. "The online dating market: Theoretical and methodological considerations." *Economic Sociology_the European Electronic Newsletter* 16.1 (2014): 11-25. Zytko, Doug, Sukeshini Grandhi, and Quentin Gad Jones. "The coaches said... what?: Analysis of online dating strategies recommended by dating coaches." *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Supporting Group Work*. ACM, 2016. DOI: 10.1145/2957276.2957287
- ix. Farvid, Panteá. "Cyber Intimacies." *The Wiley Blackwell Encyclopedia of Gender and Sexuality Studies* (2016): 1-4.
- x. Finkel, E, Eastwick, P, Benjamin, R and Reis K, 2012a, 'Online dating: a critical analysis from the perspective of psychological science', *Psychological Science in the Public Interest* 13(1):3-66 DOI: 10.1177/1529100612436522
- xi. Finkel, Eli J., et al. "Dating in a digital world." *Scientific American Mind* 23.4 (2012b): 26-33.
- xii. Zytko, Doug, Sukeshini Grandhi, and Quentin Gad Jones. "The coaches said... what?: Analysis of online dating strategies recommended by dating coaches." *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Supporting Group Work*. ACM, 2016. DOI: 10.1145/2957276.2957287
- xiii. Rosen, Devan, Pascale Roy Lafontaine, and Blake Hendrickson. "CouchSurfing: Belonging and trust in a globally cooperative online social network." *New Media & Society* 13.6 (2011): 981-998. Rosen, Devan, George A. Barnett, and Jang Hyun Kim. "Social networks and online environments: when science and practice co-evolve." *Social Network Analysis and Mining* 1.1 (2011): 27-42. Rosen, Les. "Internet based system of employment referencing and employment history verification for the creation of a human capital database." U.S. Patent Application No. 10/699,724. Kluemper, Donald H., Peter A. Rosen, and Kevin W. Mossholder. "Social networking websites, personality ratings, and the organizational context: More than meets the eye? 1." *Journal of Applied Social Psychology* 42.5 (2012): 1143-1172. Stefanone, Michael A., Derek Lackaff, and Devan Rosen. "The relationship between traditional mass media and "social media": Reality television as a model for social network site behavior." *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media* 54.3 (2010): 508-525. Stefanone, Michael A., Derek Lackaff, and Devan Rosen. "Contingencies of self-worth and social-networking-site behavior." *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking* 14.1-2 (2011): 41-49.
- xiv. Hancock, Jeffrey T., and Catalina L. Toma. "Putting your best face forward: The accuracy of online dating photographs." *Journal of Communication* 59.2 (2009): 367-386. Toma, Catalina L., and

April 30, 2019

- Jeff T. Hancock. "Lying for Love in the Modern Age: Deception in Online Dating." *The Interplay of Truth and Deception*. Routledge, 2009. 167-182.
- xv. Yurchisin, Jennifer, Kittichai Watchravesringkan, and Deborah Brown McCabe. "An exploration of identity re-creation in the context of internet dating." *Social Behavior and Personality: an international journal* 33.8 (2005): 735-750.
- xvi. Yurchisin, Jennifer, Kittichai Watchravesringkan, and Deborah Brown McCabe. "An exploration of identity re-creation in the context of internet dating." *Social Behavior and Personality: an international journal* 33.8 (2005): 735-750.
- xvii. Hardey, Michael. a. "Mediated relationships." *Information, Communication & Society* 7.2 (2004): 207-222. Hardey, Michael. b. "Digital life stories: Auto/biography in the information age." *Auto/biography* 12.3 (2004): 183-200.
- xviii. Houran, James, et al. "Do online matchmaking tests work? An assessment of preliminary evidence for a publicized 'predictive model of marital success'." *North American Journal of Psychology* 6.3 (2004).
- xix. Rosen, Larry D., et al. "The impact of emotionality and self-disclosure on online dating versus traditional dating." *Computers in Human Behavior* 24.5 (2008): 2124-2157.
- xx. Hardey, Michael. b. "Digital life stories: Auto/biography in the information age." *Auto/biography* 12.3 (2004): 183-200.
- xxi. Miller, K. *Communication Theories: Perspectives, Processes, and Contexts*. (2nd ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill, 2005.
- xxii. Brown, K., 2015, Critics Challenge the 'Science' behind Online Dating, <https://www.sfchronicle.com/style/article/Critics-challenge-the-science-behind-online-6115202.php>
- xxiii. Tcholakian, Ed, H. "Débarcadère de Trebizonde." (2018). <https://www.scribd.com/document/235147095/%>
- xxiv. Walters, Mikel, Jieru Chen, and Matthew Breiding. "National Intimate Partner and Sexual Violence Survey 2010: Findings on Victimization by Sexual Orientation." (2011). https://webcache.googleusercontent.com/search?q=cache:OxYAR5ECEZwJ:https://www.cdc.gov/violenceprevention/pdf/nisvs_sofindings.pdf+&cd=1&hl=en&ct=clnk&gl=cm
- xxv. Gunter, Barrie. "The study of online relationships and dating." *The Oxford Handbook of Internet Studies*. 2013. DOI:10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199589074.013.0009 Günther, Wendy Arianne, et al. "Debating big data: A literature review on realizing value from big data." *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems* 26.3 (2017): 191-209.
- xxvi. Zytka, Doug, Sukeshini Grandhi, and Quentin Gad Jones. "The coaches said... what?: Analysis of online dating strategies recommended by dating coaches." *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Supporting Group Work*. ACM, 2016. DOI: 10.1145/2957276.2957287
- xxvii. Bäck, Emma A., et al. "From I to We: Group formation and linguistic adaptation in an online xenophobic forum." (2018). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323736829_From_I_to_We_Group_Formation_and_Linguistic_Adaptation_in_an_Online_Xenophobic_Forum
- xxviii. Markus, Hazel. "The effect of mere presence on social facilitation: An unobtrusive test." *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology* 14.4 (1978): 389-397.
- xxix. Beck, Julie. "The Rise of Dating App Fatigue." *The Atlantic Online* (2016). <https://www.theatlantic.com/health/archive/2016/10/the-unbearable-exhaustion-of-dating-apps/505184/>
- xxx. Weigel, Moira. *Labor of love: The invention of dating*. Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2017.
- xxxi. Sternberg, R.. "A Triangular Theory of Love." *Psychological Review*. American Psychological Association, Inc., 1986

April 30, 2019

- xxxii. Sternberg, Robert J. "Triangulating Love". In Oord, T. J. (ed.). *The Altruism Reader: Selections from Writings on Love, Religion, and Science*. West Conshohocken, PA: Templeton Foundation, 2007
- xxxiii. Sternberg, Robert J. "Construct validation of a triangular love scale." *European Journal of Social Psychology* 27.3 (1997): 313-335 Sternberg, Robert J. "A Triangular Theory of Love", in H. T. Reis/C. E. Rusbult eds., *Close Relationships*, Philadelphia: Routledge, (2004) p. 266
- xxxiv. Sternberg, Robert. "Cupid's Arrow - the Course of Love through Time", London: Cambridge University Press (1986) ISBN 0-521-47893-6 Sternberg, Robert J. "Liking versus Loving" *Psychological Bulletin* (1987) p. 341
- xxxv. Sternberg, Robert. "Cupid's Arrow - the Course of Love through Time", London: Cambridge University Press (1998) ISBN 0-521-47893-6
- xxxvi. Sternberg, Robert J. "A Triangular Theory of Love", in H. T. Reis/C. E. Rusbult eds., *Close Relationships*, Philadelphia: Routledge, (2004) p. 266
- xxxvii. Ngongwikuo J, *Taboo Love, Yaounde: SOPECAM, (1985)*.
- xxxviii. Acker, Michele, and Mark H. Davis. "Intimacy, passion and commitment in adult romantic relationships: A test of the triangular theory of love." *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships* 9.1 (1992): 21-50.
- xxxix. Lomas, Tim. "The flavours of love: A cross-cultural lexical analysis." *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour* 48.1 (2018): 134-152.
- xl. Atanga, George. *The Last Of The Virgins*, Mankon: Langaa Publishers, 1985.
- xli. Ngarka, T., *The Herbalist*, Limbe: Trans-Media Communication, (1988).
- xl.ii. Nana Prah, *Destiny Mine*, Amazon.com: Decadent Publishing Company, LLC, 2015. ISBN-13: 978-161333818
- xl.iii. Whitman Myne, *A Heart to Mend*, Amazon: Authorhouse, 2009.
- xl.ii. Dinslage, Sabine. "Traditional Education and Oral Literature: A Comparative Study of the Transmission of Moral Codes of Sexual Behaviour in Folktales." *African Oral Literature: Functions in Contemporary Contexts* (2001): 46-53.
- xl.v. Foucault, Michel, *The History of Sexuality, An Introduction, vol. 1*. London: Allen Lane, (1979) [1976].
- xl.vi. _____ *Power/knowledge: Selected Interviews and Other Writings 1972-1977*. 1980.
i. Edited by C. Gordon. Brighton. Harvester Press.
- xl.vii. _____ *The History of Sexuality: The Use of Pleasure, vol. 2*, London:
i. Penguin Books. 1992) [1984].
- xl.viii. _____ *The History of Sexuality: The Care of the Self, vol. 3:*
i. London: Penguin Books. 1990) [1984].
- xl.ix. Goodwin, Robin. *Personal Relationships Across Cultures*. London: Routledge, 2013.
- l. Amara Nicole Okolo, *Black Sparkle Romance*, Lagos: Ankara Press, 2014.
- li. Awonubi, Ola. *Love's Persuasion*, Australia: Barnes & Noble, 2016
- lii. Thula, Amina. *Elevator Kiss: A Tale of Love*, Lagos: Ankara Press, 2015.
- liii. Azie Amaka. 2019. *Love At First Sound*, Nigeria: Love Africa Press, ISBN: 9781916154605
- liv. Affinnih Oyindamola. *A Tailor-made Romance*, Lagos: Ankara Press, 2015
- lv. Iwunze-Ibiam Chioma. *Finding Love Again*, Australia: Barnes & Noble, 2016
- lvi. Levine, Timothy R., Krystyna Strzyzewski Aune, and Hee Sun Park. "Love styles and communication in relationships: Partner preferences, initiation, and intensification." *Communication Quarterly* 54.4 (2006): 465-486.
- lvii. Byrne, Barbara M., Pierre Baron, and T. Leanne Campbell. "The Beck Depression Inventory (French version): Testing for gender-invariant factorial structure for nonclinical adolescents." *Journal of Adolescent Research* 9.2 (1994): 166-179.
- lviii. Gowon, Sifa Asani. (2015). "A taste of love." Abuja. Publisher: Ankara Press. ISBN: 9789785315158;9785315150; 9789785315158.

April 30, 2019

- lix. Baumeister, Roy F., and Dianne M. Tice. "Point-counterpoints: Anxiety and social exclusion." *Journal of social and clinical Psychology* 9.2 (1990): 165-195
- lx. Azie. Amaka. *Melodies of Love, Australia: Barnes & Noble, 2016.*
- lxi. Fenichel. Otto. *The Psychoanalytic Theory of Neurosis, London: Routledge & Kegan Paul Ltd, 1963*
- lxii. Skynner, R and J. Cleese, *Life and How to Survive It, USA: Mandarin, 1994.*
- lxiii. Kuhn, Thomas. *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions, Chicago: University of Chicago, 1970.*
- lxiv. Ahuvia, Aaron C., and Mara B. Adelman. "Formal intermediaries in the marriage market: A typology and review." *Journal of Marriage and the Family* (1992): 452-463.
- lxv. Scott, Veronica M., Karen E. Mottarella, and Maria J. Lavooy. "Does virtual intimacy exist? A brief exploration into reported levels of intimacy in online relationships." *CyberPsychology & Behavior* 9.6 (2006): 759-761.
- lxvi. Simenauer, Jacqueline, and David Carroll. *Singles: The New Americans. New York: Simon & Schuster, 1982.*
- lxvii. Adelman, Mara B., and Aaron C. Ahuvia. "Mediated channels for mate seeking: A solution to involuntary singlehood?." *Critical Studies in Media Communication* 8.3 (1991): 273-289
- lxviii. Woll, Stanley B., and P. Chris Cozby. "Videodating and other alternatives to traditional methods of relationship initiation." *Advances in Personal Relationships* 1 (1987): 69-108
- lxix. Woll, Stanley B., and P. Chris Cozby. "Videodating and other alternatives to traditional methods of relationship initiation." *Advances in Personal Relationships* 1 (1987): 69-108
- lxx. Adelman, Mara B., and Aaron C. Ahuvia. "Mediated channels for mate seeking: A solution to involuntary singlehood?." *Critical Studies in Media Communication* 8.3 (1991): 273-289
- lxxi. Tassie, Gregor, Kirill Kondrashin: *His Life in Music. Lanham, MD: Scarecrow Press, 2010.*
- lxxii. Badiou, Alain., *Éloge de l'amour, Paris : Flammarion, 2009.*
- lxxiii. Bakhtin Mikhail., *The Dialogic Imagination: Four Essays, ed M. Holquist, trans. Austin, Texas: University of Texas Press, 1982.*
- lxxiv. _____ *Problems of Dostoevsky's Poetics, (Theory and History of Literature, vol. 8). Edited and translated by C. Emerson. Manchester. Manchester University Press, 1984.*
- lxxv. _____ *Speech Genres and Other Late Essays. Trans. by V.W. McGee. Austin. University of Texas Press, 1986.*
- lxxvi. Levine, Norman. "Two Unpublished Manuscripts by Karl Marx." *Central European History* 9.3 (1976): 294-297.
- lxxvii. Foucault, Michel, *The History of Sexuality, An Introduction, vol. 1. London: Allen Lane, (1979) [1976].*
- lxxviii. _____ *Power/knowledge: Selected Interviews and Other Writings 1972-1977. 1980. Edited by C. Gordon. Brighton. Harvester Press.*
- lxxix. _____ *The History of Sexuality: The Use of Pleasure, vol. 2, London: Penguin Books. 1992) [1984].*
- lxxx. Gray, Madison Jody. "Tinder & The Marketplace of Love: Summer 2016 Research." https://scholar.googleusercontent.com/scholar?q=cache:yXJNRDWZeiYJ:scholar.google.com/+Online+Dating:+Surviving+the+love+Apocalypse+2016&hl=en&as_sdt=0,5
- lxxxi. Bethuel, E., 2018, *Science Finally proves True a Common Theory about Online Dating* <https://www.inverse.com/article/47884-it-s-all-about-the-desirability-gap>
- lxxxii. Austen, Jane. 1993, *Pride and prejudice, Hertfordshire: Wordsworth Editions Limited. ISBN 9781853260001.*
- lxxxiii. Hakim, Catherine. "Erotic capital." *European Sociological Review* 26.5 (2010): 499-518.
- lxxxiv. Ambanasom Shadrach, *Homage and Courtship: Romantic Stirrings of a Young Man, Mankon: Langaa Publishers, 2010*

April 30, 2019

- lxxxv. Luhmann, Nikolas., *Love as symbolically generalised medium of communication*, In J. C.Jacobsen, (red.), *Autopoiesis II. Selected texts by Niklas Luhmann*, København: Politisk revy, 1995.
- lxxxvi. _____ *Trust: A mechanism for reduction of social complexity*, København: Hans Reitzels forlag, 1999.
- lxxxvii. _____ *Social Systems – sketches for a general theory*, København: Hans Reitzels Forlag, 2000.
- lxxxviii. Ricoeur, Paul. "Construing and Constructing: A Review of the aims of interpretation by ED Hirsh." *A Ricoeur Reader: Reflections and Imaginations*. New York, London, Toronto, Sydney, Tokyo, Singapore: Harvester Wheatsheaf (1991).
- lxxxix. Bjerrum Nielsen, Harriet. "Seductive texts with serious intentions." *Educational Researcher* 24.1 (1995): 4-12.
- xc. Castells, Manuel. *The Rise of the Network Society*. Vol. 12. John Wiley & Sons, 2011.
- xci. Gadamer, Hans-Georg. *Dialogue and Dialectic: Eight Hermeneutical Studies on Plato*. Yale University Press, 1983.
- xcii. Garrison, Jim. *Dewey and Eros: Wisdom and Desire in the Art of Teaching* New York: Teachers College Press, 1997.
- xciii. Hooks, Bell. "Teaching to transgress: Education as the practice of freedom." *Journal of Leisure Research* 28.4 (1996): 316.

Sketch bio

Alfred Ndi holds a *Doctorat d'État* Degree in postcolonial digital humanities with special interest in continental literatures. Beyond the dialectics of *praxis/theory* in the digital marketing of race, class, ethnicity, gender, sexuality, generation, disability, nation, etc, he investigates the problematics of the hypertext in the dynamics of power/ knowledge in ICT political economy. His long term goal is to develop a critical archival database flexible enough to illuminate all the humanities discourses for outreach educational purposes and to contribute to the foundations of global peace.

He has published papers on the building, breaking and sharing ethos in critical studies in many academic journals and books.